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MARKET PENETRATION OF FMCG AND REGIONAL PRODUCTS IN THE RURAL MARKETS - WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS

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Abstract:

Consumer goods companies are employing different market penetration strategies to increase their organizational growth. The aim of the research study was to study the Market penetration of FMCG and Regional Products in the rural market. This research was guided by the following objectives: To find out the brand preference of consumers in FMCG and Regional Products, to measure the factors influencing of consumers in the purchase of various FMCG and Regional Products and to identify the problems faced by the consumers while consuming the products and to offer suitable suggestions for the effective penetration of the products in the rural market. The researcher has followed empirical research design and collected data from 300 respondents by using convenient non-random sampling method. The data were analyzed with the help of Percentage analysis and Garrett’s ranking method and the results are presented in the form of tables. The results indicated that FMCG products have a larger share than the regional products. Regional products have low penetration but huge growth potential. So the manufacturing companies are responsible for all problems and also they are taking necessary steps to improve and fulfill the needs and wants of the consumers. At the same time, the consumer products companies should be ethical in manufacturing in their products. The researcher recommended that all the strategies are a prerequisite for organizational growth and they complement each other.

Keywords: Rural Marketing, Rural Consumers, Market Penetration, FMCG and Regional Products, Brand preference.

1. Introduction

Marketing is the process of identifying, anticipating and knowing customer needs and organizing all the resources of the company to satisfy them. Satisfying the customer’s need is a primary condition of marketing and essential for the existence of any organization. In order to achieve the marketing goals, knowledge of consumer behavior is the must. The consumer’s behavior comprises the acts, processes and social relationships exhibited by individuals, groups, and organizations in searching, obtainment, use of, and consequent experience with products and services. An understanding and knowledge of the motives underlying consumer behavior help a firm in seeking better and more effective ways to satisfy its customers. It helps to select appropriate sales and advertising strategies and to plan

marketing program in a more efficient manner. In today's competitive environment where the customer has got a tremendous choice for selecting brands, it is a very challenging task for a marketer to attract new customers and to retain the old customers. For this purpose, the marketer uses marketing penetration strategies to position their product in the minds of the customer and establish their brand image in the market.

2. Market Penetration

Market penetration is both a measure and a strategy. A business will utilize a market penetration strategy to attempt to penetrate in an existing market. The goal is to get in quickly with the product or service and capture a large share of the market. Market penetration is also a measure of the percentage of the market that the product or service is able to capture. A marketing penetration strategy involves the increased sale of already existing products to a market that is already in existence. This is in an effort to acquire a bigger market share than the organization's competitors. In this regard, market penetration offers the organizations an opportunity to increase both their sales as well as revenue. The extent to which a product is recognized and bought by customers in a particular market is called market penetration. Market penetration is the strategy of a firm to intrude the market of an existing product. The measure to ensure market penetration could be offering lower prices, providing volume discounts or bundling.

3. Fast Moving Consumer Goods

Fast Moving Consumer Goods are those goods that are consumed every day by the average consumer and are replaced or fully used up over a short period of days, weeks, or months, and within one year. The fast-moving consumer goods also known as consumer packaged goods (CPG) are products that have a quick turnover and relatively low cost. Though the absolute profit made on FMCG products is relatively small, they generally sell in large numbers and so the cumulative profit on such products can be large.

4. Personal Care Products

Personal care products or a toiletry is the industry which manufactures consumer products used in personal hygiene and for beautification. Such products are Oral care, hair care, skin care, cosmetics/deodorants, perfumes, feminine hygiene, baby care, shower products, etc.

5. Statement of the Problem

In a competitive world, there are many problems in marketing of goods. Some problems can be solved, but many problems may not be solved. India is a developing country. So, most of the people are living in rural areas. Rural marketing is important for developing a country's economy. Manufacturers face many problems in marketing their product in rural areas because most of the rural consumers earn low incomes, have low levels of literacy, low levels of brand awareness, communication, and transportation facilities. Consumer behavior is not as simple as what many think. It is highly complex and cannot predict how consumers will react towards products while buying it. To understand the buying behavior of rural consumers, we must go into market penetration aspects.

Market Penetration of consumer goods is deemed to be important to understand the consumption pattern and preference of different rural consumers. Understanding the consumers' preference would help the firms in formulating the strategies to cater to the needs of the consumers and thereby increasing their market share. Consumers' standard of living and lifestyle are found to change rapidly, especially in a dynamic environment. Hence it is an interesting aspect to analyze which brands are consumed by the rural consumer, how much they buy, what they prefer, from which sources they get information about the products and so on. The rural consumers are finding various problems to select their consumer goods. It is identified that there is a need for research work in the

field of market penetration of consumer goods in the rural market of Dindigul. Thus, in order to find answers to the following questions, the researcher has undertaken this study.

1. What are the brand preference of consumers in FMCG and Regional products?
2. What are the factors that influence the consumers in the purchase of various FMCG and Regional products?
3. What are the problems faced by the consumers while consuming the products?

In order to probe into these factors, the researcher has made an attempt on the present study entitled *“Market Penetration of FMCG and Regional Products in the Rural Market - with special Reference to Personal Care Products”*.

6. Objectives of the study

- To find out the brand preference of consumers in FMCG and Regional Products.
- To measure the factors influencing of consumers in the purchase of various FMCG and Regional Products.
- To identify the problems faced by the consumers while consuming the products and offer suitable suggestion for effective penetration in rural market

7. Research Methodology

300 Samples respondents have been collected through convenient Sampling method in Dindigul. The raw data entered in SPSS and the analysis was carried forward. The data was checked for reliability and validity. The result showed 0.7 Cronbach Alpha value confirming the validity of the test instrument. Simple Percentage Method and Garrett’s ranking method are used.

From the above **Table.1**, it is clear that 172 (57.33 percent) respondents are males, 140 (46.67percent) respondents fall under the age group of 25 to 40 years,170 (56.67 percent) have studied up to Higher Secondary level, 120 (40.00percent) respondents are Farmers. Further, there are 175 (58.33 percent) respondents whose family income monthly is less than ₹ 10,000.

8. Brand Preference for Personal Care Products

For analysis purposes, the researcher has selected 5 items only, under the category of Personal Care Products. They are Bathing Soap, Shampoo, Hair Oil, Tooth Paste, and Tooth Brush. In Dindigul area, various branded products, local brands, and unbranded items are also available. The brand preferences of the respondents towards the bathing soap in the study area are presented in the following Table 2.

Table. 1: Profile of the Respondents

Particulars		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Males	172	57.33
	Females	128	42.67
	Total	300	100.00
Age	Below 25Years	40	13.33
	25 to 40 Years	140	46.67
	Above 40 years	120	40.00
	Total	300	100.00
Educational Qualification	Higher secondary level	170	56.67
	Graduate	110	36.67
	Post Graduate	20	06.66
	Total	300	100.00
Occupation	Farmer	120	40.00
	Labour	80	26.67
	Private Employee	40	13.33
	Govt Employee	30	10.00
	Business	30	10.00
	Total	300	100.00
Family income (₹)	Up to 10,000	175	58.33
	10,001 to 20,000	100	33.33
	Above 25,000	25	08.34
	Total	300	100.00

It can be found from the above **Table. 2** that, out of 300 respondents, 275 (91.66 percent) respondents are using FMCG products and only a few respondents (8.33 percent) are using regional products regarding bathing soap. In this case, FMCG products are having the highest penetration in the rural market.

Table. 2: Brand Preference of the Respondents towards Bathing Soap

Particulars	Brand Name	Frequency	Total
Bathing Soap	FMCG Products		
	Hamam	90	
	Lifebuoy	52	
	Cinthol	33	
	Mysore Sandal	60	
	Dove	40	275
	Regional Products		
	Herbal Soap		15
	Unbranded		10
	Not Usage		0
	Total		300

Table. 3: Brand Preference of the Respondents towards Shampoo

Particulars	Brand Name	Frequency	Percentage
Shampoo	FMCG Products		
	Clini plus	110	
	All clear	60	
	Dove	40	
	Sun silk	35	
	Meera Herbal	15	
	Karthiga	15	265
	Regional Products		
	Herbal powder		10
	Unbranded		15
	Not Usage		0
	Total		400

It can be found from the above **Table.3** that, out of 300 respondents, 265 (88.33 percent) respondents are using FMCG products and only a few respondents (8.33 percent) are using regional products regarding Shampoo. It shows that FMCG products are having the highest penetration in the rural market.

Table. 4: Brand Preference of the Respondents towards Hair oil

Particulars	Brand Name	Frequency	Percentage
Hair oil	FMCG Products		
	Parachute	110	
	VVD	90	
	Amla - red Dabur	25	
	Total		225
	Regional Products		
	Cold Pressed oil		25
	Unbranded		50
	Not Usage		0
	Total		300

It can be found from the above **Table.4** that, out of 300 respondents, 225 (75.00 percent) respondents are using FMCG products and one-fourth of the respondents (25.00 percent) are using regional products regarding Hair oil. It shows that FMCG products are having the highest penetration in the rural market.

It can be found from the above **Table.5** that, out of 300 respondents, 260 (86.67 percent) respondents are using FMCG products and only a few (5.00 percent) are using regional products regarding Tooth Paste and (8.33 percent) respondents are not using any kind of brand. This analysis shows that FMCG products are having the highest penetration in the rural market

Table. 5: Brand Preference of the Respondents towards Tooth Paste

Particulars	Brand Name	Frequency	Percentage
Tooth Paste	FMCG Products		
	Colgate	210	
	Pepsodent	25	
	Vicco	25	
	Total		260
	Regional Products		
	Regional		0
	Unbranded		15
	Not Usage		25
	Total		300

Table. 6: Brand Preference of the Respondents towards Tooth Brush

Particulars	Brand Name	Frequency	Percentage
Tooth Brush	FMCG Products		
	Colgate	201	
	Oral -B	74	
	Total		275
	Regional Products		
	Regional		0
	Unbranded		15
	Not Usage		10
	Total		300

It can be found from the above **Table.6** that, out of 300 respondents, 275 (91.66 percent) respondents are using FMCG products and only a few (5.00 percent) are using regional products regarding Toothbrush and (3.33 percent) are not using any kind of brand regarding toothbrush. It shows that FMCG products are having the highest penetration in the rural market.

Table. 7: Factors Influencing the Consumer’s Preference towards FMCG and Regional Products

S.No	Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	No opinion	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Rank
1	Quality	900	300	50	8	0	1258	III
2	Price	800	620	7	6	16	1449	I
3	Package	600	358	75	10	3	1046	V
4	Availability	500	250	52	2	5	809	VI
5	Awareness	200	300	17	0	0	517	X
6	Long Lasting products	500	600	24	20	8	1152	IV
7	Shop Keeper’s Recommendation	440	220	38	62	8	768	VII
8	Free offers / Sales promotions	320	200	48	5	30	603	IX
9	Shelf display	250	300	50	7	28	635	VIII
10	Friends and family recommendation	750	422	110	6	0	1288	II

It is observed from the **Table. 7** that, analysis of the overall opinion of the respondents regarding factors influencing the consumer’s preference towards FMCG and Regional products that “ price “has the highest score of 1449 and it ranks first. The factor, “Friends and family recommendation” is with the score of 1288, holding the second rank. “Quality “with the score of 1258 holds the third rank.” Long lasting products” with the total score of 1152 holds the fourth rank among the various problems. As far as “Package “is concerned it is with the score of 1046 holding the Fifth rank. The “Availability “holds the sixth rank with a total score of 809. The Factor “Shop Keeper’s Recommendation “holds the seventh rank among the various factors with a total score of 768 and “ Shelf display “ with the score of 635 holds the eighth rank. “Free offers / Sales promotions “has the total score of 603 and it ranks ninth. “Awareness “holds the tenth rank with the total score of 517.

9. Problems

In India, consumer goods industry is growing day by day with a lot of competition because the consumers are highly dynamic even in the consumption of one single product. All people are buying these products because it meets their standard of living and lifestyle. But at the same time, it can be said that the users are not deriving benefits out of these products all the time. They do face certain problems in using them because these products are not 100 percent safe and useful. They do face certain problems in using them because these products are not 100 percent safe and useful. Some of the common problems, faced by the respondents while consuming the products, such as lack of awareness, Non – availability of the expected brand, People are affected by health problem, Not genuine as advertised, High cost etc., based on the above-stated problems and observations made during this study, some suggestions are given by the researcher to of effective marketing penetration in the rural market.

10. Suggestions and conclusion

Rural consumers are more dynamic. Their taste, needs, and preferences are changing as per the current scenario. The consumers now look for product differentiation and the convenience offered. The consumer has a certain expectation from branded items in terms of its quality, price and packaging and awareness about the products. In case of Regional, Products do not fulfill their desires and the status of regional products needs to change and fulfill consumer's needs and wants. According to research revealed that FMCG products penetration is high in personal care product categories whereas regional products penetration is very low. Regional products are having many problems such as low investment, lack of manpower, inefficient communication, running the business without a license, overall backwardness, and preference for a conventional way of life of the rural people, such factors must be tackled aptly as these have been hindering the growth of companies in the rural regions. Regional products companies have better knowledge of rural marketing and work out appropriate marketing strategies for the success not only in the short run but also in the long run. Hence, FMCG products categories are high in demand and giving immense growth in the rural market. On the basis of findings of the present study, the following suggestions are made.

11. References

1. Jyoti Pradhan (2014) "Rural Brand Awareness and Preference of FMCGs", IOSR Journal of Business and Management, 6.
2. Rajam(2015) "A study on rural consumer Satisfaction of FMCG in Coimbatore District", International Journal of Management and Social Science, 03.
3. Alamelu (2016) "Factors influencing Purchase of FMCG products among Urban and Rural consumers", Indian Journal of Science and Technology, 9.
4. Baring S(2009) "Attitude and behavior of rural consumers towards branded FMCG Products", Indian Journal of Marketing, 39 (5).
5. Indian Rural Market 2015/industry.aspx (Accenture)
6. Yuvarani,"A study on rural consumer behavior towards selected fast moving consumer goods in salam District. [http.handle.net](http://handle.net).
7. Discovering statistics using SPSS, 2nd ED Sage, London.
8. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/cronbach's_alpha
9. [www. Google.com](http://www.Google.com)
10. [www. Research gate.com](http://www.Research_gate.com)
11. www.IBEF.org.com